

FORMS AND CHARACTERISTICS OF ORGANIZATION OF LEARNING CLASSES IN GENERAL SCIENCES

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Abstract. *In the following article the methodics of teaching the issues of energy supplies in the agriculture and irrigation. The new innovational technologies of supply of energy are discussed. The proposals are given based on the scales of national and international experience.*

Keywords: *the innovational technologies of teaching the syllabus of energetic, supply of electric energy, “Smart water” technologies, water sector, project “Modernization of agricultural sector”, Vestas Wind Systems A/S, Siemens Gamensa Renewable Energy A/S, usage of electric energy in pumping stations.*

Introduction: In the introductory report of the subject "Electrical Engineering" in the training of electricians in the field of "Electric Power Engineering" the role of science in the training of junior specialists, specific directions are given to get a holistic view of the science.

To acquaint students with the tasks and objectives of the subject "Electrical Engineering" to determine the place and role of junior specialists in the system of vocational training in manufacturing enterprises, to give a brief overview of the science, the achievements of science and the development of "Electrical Engineering" in Uzbekistan and abroad. it would be expedient to introduce the names of well-known scientists of the states.

In the introductory report, the teacher will determine the direction of future research in the field, provide an analysis of the literature based on the results of educational and methodological and research work recommended for the study of

science, deadlines and forms of reporting and evaluation of theoretical, practical and laboratory work. defines

Informing students on the topic of the lecture is a traditional traditional type of lecture for students to study a specific topic of "Electrical Engineering". The science teacher should describe and explain the learning information needed to convey the topic approved in the work program to the students.

The commentary forms the basis of the theoretical ideas expressed in the report, the scientific concepts for the deep understanding of science, and the conceptual basis of the whole science or department. Particular attention is paid to the achievements and shortcomings of scientific research in the field of "Electrical Engineering", the development of the field of electricity, energy efficiency.

In the presentation of the commentary, the fact that the science teacher systematizes scientific knowledge related to the development of the energy sector, fully justifies the interdependence of general disciplines.

In a problem report, new knowledge with the development of science is given through a question, an issue, a problem situation. At the same time, the student's learning process with the teacher is closer to scientific research. an analysis of contemporary perspectives on doing so would be appropriate.

Visual presentation This form of presentation is aimed at presenting visual materials and giving clear and concise comments on them. Pedagogical task: to provide new educational information with the help of teaching aids and audio and video equipment.

A binary (two-person) lecture consists of a teacher-student dialogue between two teachers or a representative of two academic schools. At the same time, science teachers participating in the two-person lecture on "Electrical Engineering" should highlight the problematic aspects of the topic, covering the content of new educational information on the topic "Calculation of electrical circuits" planned in the curriculum.

In some cases, pre-planned erroneous lectures are held in order to master the subject and acquire knowledge and skills. At the end of the lecture, the audience is diagnosed and the mistakes made are checked. The science teacher should cover the content of the new material covered in the lecture, encourage students to constantly monitor the information provided.

The lecture will be held at the conference as part of the curriculum as a scientific-practical lesson, consisting of a set of problems and a system of lectures (5-10 minutes) related to the transfer of science. The reports should focus on a comprehensive coverage of the problem identified in the discipline of "Electrical Engineering". At the end of the lesson, the teacher summarizes, completes and clarifies the independent work and lectures of students.

The process of assimilation of disciplines included in the curriculum of the elective course "Electric Power Engineering" in the consultative reports can take place using different scenarios. For example, a) Conducting a scenario "Question-Answer" on the subject, in which the teacher of science after answering all the lectures on the whole subject program answers questions on the course or on a particular section of the subject.

2) Focused on perfect mastery of the science being taught

Conclusion on the second section

1. The use of pedagogical and information technologies in the teaching of general sciences allows to define the concepts and ideas of the science, to express the identified ideas and the connections between them.

2. Problematic presentation of educational material from the disciplines of the curriculum is a stimulus for students to change their attention to the process of acquiring new knowledge and to form their creative activity.

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